

UDC 338.43.

**FORMATION OF NEW ECONOMIC RELATIONS IS THE KEY TO
STABLE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE**

*Burkhanov Alisher Khadzhimuradovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences,
Associate Professor, Gulistan State University, Gulistan, Uzbekistan,
alisher892jentra@gmail.com*

Abstract: *an overview of the trends and new economic attitudes of agriculture in Uzbekistan is given. Evaluated the achievement of new economic relations of agriculture.*

Key words: *innovation, agricultural economics, sustainable development, transformation of agriculture.*

Introduction

In recent years, intensive, qualitatively new structural and market reforms have been carried out in the economy of Uzbekistan, the priorities of the country's socio-economic development have been radically revised, new, practical drivers of economic growth are being introduced that have the power to really move the economy. Old, obsolete institutions and instruments of economic regulation are giving way to new, innovative and effective forms and methods of influencing the economy.

Today, innovation and research in every field is an important factor in achieving new achievements and creating a healthy competitive environment. In particular, the reform of the agricultural sector in our country and the rational use of modern methods in agriculture are yielding positive results. In recent years, much attention has been paid to the consistent introduction of market relations and practical experience, tested in world practice and of great importance in the development of the economy. One of them is the cluster system, and now the issue of establishing the activity of this system in the field of cotton growing, textile and light industry of our economy is defined as a priority [8].

The agro-industrial complex is a large intersectoral and multifunctional system that unites various aspects of economic activity. However, for a complete understanding of the processes taking place in the agro-industrial complex, for a complete justification of the organization and management of these processes, it is important to fully understand the structure of the agro-industrial complex.

For a rather important period, the agricultural (agricultural) sector was considered separately from the sectors providing services in agriculture, including the sale of food products, but by the 70s of the 20th century these ideas were, since today

most agricultural resources are used in industry, processed and is delivered to consumers through specialized retail chains with a wide network infrastructure.

In highly developed countries, the share of a growing economy in the increase in the share of marketable products of the food complex does not exceed 20-30, a higher share of marketable products falls on the distribution and distribution of products to consumers.

Literature analysis

Developing a long-term development strategy plays an important role in the strategic planning of the country's economic development. In recent decades, the interest of scientists and practitioners in predicting socio-economic processes and developing development strategies at the global and national level has increased significantly. This is done by international organizations, scientific centers, and various organizations in foreign countries, and they are developing long-term global development trends and scenarios [6].

While studying the scientific research of foreign scientists in the agrarian field, for example, the Russian scientist A.V. Chayanov, "Nowadays, it is an important issue for science to theoretically justify the development of agriculture in the long-term perspective. it is necessary to apply a methodology that includes socio-economic, political and cultural changes to the processes [7]. In our opinion, it is important to take into account these scientific and practical proposals that are of strategic importance in the development of agriculture in our country. It is also necessary to ensure the implementation of necessary measures related to the modernization and development of agriculture in our country, which will serve to increase the efficiency of agricultural production.

Initially, the agro-industrial complex was considered to include agriculture and processing industries, and the products produced by this complex included food, leather, textiles, tobacco, and the like. Russian researchers N.E. Smetanina, V.A. Tikhonova, M.Ya., such as Lemesheva, who conducted scientific research on the network structure of the agro-industrial complex in the 80s of the last century, proposed dividing the agro-industrial complex into three areas [3]:

- the service sector (various enterprises of mechanical engineering, repair of agricultural machinery, logistics of agriculture, construction, training, etc.);
- agriculture (plant growing and animal husbandry);
- food industry.

Main results

The Economic Research Service of the US Department of Agriculture, which dealt with these issues at that time, paid special attention to the classification of the provision of various services to agricultural producers, including transportation services, along with the above three areas. In this regard, domestic scientists and specialists, who have activated scientific research, propose to divide it into five areas, to approach the classification of the agro-industrial complex more deeply. Briefly, this approach looks like this:

- 1) agriculture;
- 2) repair of machinery and equipment, production of mineral fertilizers and feed, construction work in rural areas;
- 3) branches of the processing industry and light industry;
- 4) material and technical support of trade branches, catering establishments, agriculture;
- 5) production service, quarantine service.

In the late 90s of the last century, it was proposed to supplement the composition of the agro-industrial complex with a system of commodity-money transactions and information support. In modern research work, marketing in the field of agriculture, communication associations in the countryside, support for the agro-industrial complex on a scientific basis, public administration and regulation of the complex are provided here.

Thus, AFM appears as an extremely large-scale and multifaceted system. Although more than a third of the sectors of the national economy are inextricably linked with the agricultural sector, today the state.

In particular, the message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis is emphasized, “..... the priority task is to increase the profitability of a hectare of land from the current average of \$2,000 to at least \$5,000. To do this, it is necessary to widely introduce the most advanced scientific developments and innovations into agriculture, including agricultural technologies, water-saving technologies, biotechnologies, and achievements in seed production.” [1]

In 2021, the share of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in the structure of GDP amounted to 26%. The share of people employed in agriculture, forestry and fisheries is 26%.

Share of agriculture in GDP 2017-2021 reduced due to the development of industry and services. In particular, the share of agriculture in GDP in 2017 was 34 percent, and by 2021 it will decrease to 26 percent [9].

Table 1. Dynamics of the volume of agricultural production in Uzbekistan (billion. soum)

	2000	2005	2010	2015	2017	2020	2021
Agricultural products, billion. Soum	1387,2	5978,3	30856,7	99604,6	148199,3	250250,6	303415,5
crop production	696,8	3323,1	18119,0	55429,2	83303,4	123858,8	152130,4
animal husbandry	690,4	2655,2	12737,7	44175,4	64895,9	126391,8	151285,1

Source: Compiled by the author based on the material Agency of Statistics under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The growth rate of the dynamic development of agriculture shows stable development due to the accelerated reform and innovative approach in this sector.

Agriculture, in addition to being the main supplier of products and raw materials for the food and light industries, ensures the country's food and economic security, eliminates the country's dependence on imported food. Therefore, although food imports are economically beneficial, developed countries widely use various means to support their agriculture. For example, in the US, state support for farmers is 30% of their income, while in Japan it is 66%, in Norway it is 77%, and in Switzerland it is 80%. At the same time, state support for agricultural producers in our country is 10 percent, and dependence on imports for some food products is several times higher than the established norm.

In addition, one fifth of the country's population is employed in agriculture and the food industry of our country, the share of these industries in the country's GDP is about 23 percent, about 51 percent of the retail trade turnover corresponds to the contribution of food products. In conditions when about 50% of the country's population lives in rural areas, and 21% in suburban areas, agro-industrial enterprises play a crucial role in providing employment for the population.

Figure 1. Growth rates of agricultural production (% of the corresponding period of the previous year)

Source: Compiled by the author based on the material Agency of Statistics under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As can be seen from the data of Table 1, the growth rate of agricultural products has a stable development trend in the last 2019-2022 years.

Personnel, scientific developments, information support, supply of fuels and lubricants for agriculture, maintenance of agricultural machinery, soil, water, etc., necessary for the functioning of agriculture, are elements that serve the organization and development of agricultural production. A number of elements of the economy and ASM tend to have a managerial impact on agriculture.

For example, the geographical location of the region determines the specialization of agriculture, national legislation, the policy of the state and local governments on the organization and development of agricultural production, as well as the form of economic management chosen by agricultural enterprises determine the rules for interaction between ASM subjects. Increasing competition and an increase in the risk of other adverse risks are forcing enterprises to look for the most effective ways to manage production, finances and sales markets. As a result, high quality raw materials are created both for the consumption of the population and for processing industries.

The agro-industrial complex can work effectively only when all the elements of this system, as well as the interactions between them, are carried out without problems and provide producers with an acceptable income for them. But today the problems typical for the agro-industrial complex of our country significantly reduce its potential

and investment attractiveness. Although this aspect of the issue is considered in sufficient detail in the economic literature, below we will dwell on some aspects that are characteristic of the agro-industrial complex of our country.

1. Strong competitive environment. The results of agricultural producers working in the same natural and climatic conditions differ little from each other.

2. A good harvest is not completely guaranteed. Even fertile land may not produce good crops due to adverse weather conditions (this situation is more common in recent years due to climate change).

3. Seasonality, the duration of the technological process, the delay in receipt.

4. Focus on growing up to three crops. Although this approach involves the use of techniques with constant uniformity, working with the same consumers, such an approach does not justify itself in changing market conditions.

5. Low marketability of agricultural products. One of the specific economic features of agricultural production is that a certain part of the output is consumed by agriculture itself for the purpose of reproduction.

Conclusion and proposal

The priority task is to increase the profitability of a hectare of land from the current average of \$2,000 to at least \$5,000. To do this, it is necessary to widely introduce the most advanced scientific developments and innovations into agriculture, including agricultural technologies, water-saving technologies, biotechnologies, and achievements in seed production.

In our opinion, the market economic reforms carried out in recent years in many countries of the world, including Uzbekistan, are directly related to the concept of the "invisible hand of competition", developed by Smith more than two hundred years ago. Entrepreneurs economic entities to improve productivity play a major role material interests.

At present, in the conditions of the market, agriculture has turned out to be an outsider in the agro-industrial complex, and without state support for this industry, its development in the future is not possible.

In our opinion, state intervention in the economic relations of the agricultural sector should be reflected, first of all, in the implementation of market principles in the pricing policy for manufactured products.

At the same time, it should be taken into account that in the conditions of market relations, state regulation is not of a directive nature, but is implemented through a system of measures for concessional lending, pricing policy, taxes, subsidies, development of exports and imports, etc.

The agro-industrial complex can work effectively only when all the elements of this system, as well as the interactions between them, are carried out without problems and provide producers with an acceptable income for them. But today the problems typical for the agro-industrial complex of our country significantly reduce its potential and investment attractiveness.

Literature

1. Message of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyev to the Oliy Majlis. December 29, 2020 www.gov.uz.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 23, 2019 "On approval of the strategy for the development of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030". Lex.uz.
3. Cluster approach to the development of the agro-industrial complex of the Omsk region / ed. V.V. Karpova, V.V. Aleshchenko. – Novosibirsk: publishing house of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2014. – 416 p.
4. Clusters and cooperations. Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, agro.uz
5. Kurbanbabaeva N., Trends and achievements of recent years., CEIR - Journal "Economic Review" No. 9
6. The Global Trends 2030: Alternative Worlds. Report published by the US National Intelligence Council in 2013.
7. Chayanov A.V. Basic ideas and forms of organization of peasant cooperation (reprinted works). - M.: "Nauka", 1991.
8. Burkhanov A.Kh. "Economics of agriculture", textbook, 2022. 623 p.
9. Bulletin of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Agriculture of Uzbekistan 2018-2021. Tashkent - 2022. www.stat.uz.